

The Center of the Universe

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1. PROGRAM NOTES

The Center of the Universe was inspired by my impression of New York City after several trips to this world center. When I stood at the top of the Empire State Building, I felt that it absorbed the energy of the entire universe. People with different backgrounds travel to New York from all over the world, creating a colorful and spectacular city. The primary material in this work is the text “The Center of the Universe.” This text is stated and manipulated in various languages, including English, Spanish, French, German, Italian, Russian, Chinese, Japanese, Korean, and Thai. All the human voices come from the sampled AI voices of the MacOS system. Two Bluetooth Nintendo Wiimote Controllers provide the capability to stand untethered at center stage and play this composition.

2. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

The Center of the Universe is a real-time performance composition for two Nintendo Wiimote controllers, OSCulator, and Symbolic Sound’s Kyma. The Wiimote is an enormously flexible and versatile performance interface that can conveniently generate both triggers and continuous control data. Its power derives from its eleven buttons (ten on the front and one on the back) and six continuous controllers, (Pitch, Roll, and Yaw, and AccelerometerX, AccelerometerY, and AccelerometerZ).

3. MEDIA LINK

- Video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hAJYE34guck>

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